

AMC FOR UE UPLINK CONDITION WITH SC METHOD AT HETNET MACROCELL AND MICROCELL AROUND BUILDINGS

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Abstract— The UE (User Equipment) was moved around building that covered with some cell or NBs (Node BS). In this research analyzed about UE communication with frequency 10 GHz that moved around building environment. The diffraction mechanism caused by buildings that was modeled with Single Knife Edge method. UE through HetNet (Heterogeneous Networks) area from macrocell and microcell. UE propagation used uplink condition. AMC (Adaptive Modulation and Coding) that used MCS (Modulation and Code Scheme) such as QPSK, 16QAM, and 64QAM. As the result for coverage percentage when used selection combining method obtained 100%, NBs macrocell 100%, and NBs microcell 86.56%. Modulation percentages with selection combining method at UE trajectory for 64 QAM obtained 74.62%, and 64 QAM code rate 4/5 obtained 64.16%

Keywords— *HetNet, building, 10 GHz, AMC, NBs.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The macrocell coverage area of communication systems, it is difficult for covered at all area. HetNet (Heterogeneous Networks) Communication deployed with macrocell / microcell / picocell / femtocell. Some research that related with coverage area such as picocell range expansion with interference mitigation LTE heterogeneous networks [1], and resource allocation schemes for LTE femtocell [2]. The research that related with millimeter wave such as communication propagation from outdoor to indoor with AMC at 10 GHz [3], 3GPP rural microcell path loss for millimeter wave [4], propagation measurements and path loss models for THz in urban microcell [5], base station with millimeter wave for CoMP 5G [6], MS location determination that used AoA at 47 GHz [7], AMC MS at train with trajectory around building environment [8], diffraction effect caused building with millimeter wave for communication systems [9], multipath effect at MS around building environment at 47 GHz [10], cellular communication systems that used at drone with 10 GHz frequency [11], multipath propagation measurement and channel model pathloss with 142 GHz frequency around building [12].

This research an analyze about UE communication that moved around building environment. The trajectory UE traverse HetNet base station or Node Base. HetNet Node Base consist of microcell and macrocell. The HetNet diversity used selection combining method. The frequency for cellular communication systems was used 10 GHz. The UE communication propagation used uplink condition. The communication propagation influenced by diffraction mechanism from high building, atmospheric, and AWGN channel. That diffraction mechanism modeled with single knife edge method. The modulation effected by SNR from communication. AMC (Adaptive Modulation and Coding) used MCS (Modulation and Coding Scheme). MCS that used consist of QPSK, 16 QAM, and 64 QAM. Some variation code rate for QPSK consist of 1/8, 1/5, 1/4, 1/3, 1/2, 2/3, 3/4, and

4/5. Some variation code rate for 16 QAM consist of 1/2, 2/3, 3/4, dan 4/5. Some variation code rate for 64 QAM consist of 2/3, 3/4, dan 4/5.

II. METHOD

The communication systems at UE (User Equipment) moved at building environment. That building was used variation of high building. The high building caused propagation LOS or NLOS condition. NLOS condition modeled with diffraction mechanism. Single Knife Edge method was used for that diffraction mechanism. UE moved through HetNet. HetNet cell used two of Node Base, that consist of NBs macrocell and NBs microcell. The communication propagation of Node Base macrocell is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. The high of NBs was used 30m. Diversity model of NBs was used selection combining method.

UE communication systems analyzed with diffraction mechanism. Single Knife Edge method is shown in Figure 3. The equation for that method expressed in Equation (1). Some parameters such as λ (wavelength), v (kirchoff Fresnel), h (diffraction high), d_1 (distance), dan d_2 (distance) [13].

Figure. 1 Propagation from NB 1

Figure. 2 Propagation from NB 2

Figure. 3 Single Knife Edge Method

$$v = h \sqrt{\frac{d(d_1 + d_2)}{\lambda d_1 d_2}} = \alpha \sqrt{\frac{2d_1 d_2}{\lambda (d_1 + d_2)}} \quad (1)$$

The power transmitter of UE used 30 dBm, antenna gain NBs macrocell 18 dBi, and antenna gain NBs microcell 10 dBi. SNR value can be calculated using Equation (2).

$$SNR = \frac{S}{N} \quad (2)$$

Noise power was calculated from parameters such as boltzman constant, noise bandwidth of 200 MHz, noise figure of NBs macrocell 6 dB, noise figure of NBs microcell 3 dB, and noise temperature of 290°K [14]. The atmospheric attenuation can be calculated using Equation (3), that equation consist of gas attenuation, and distances (km) [14].

$$A = \gamma r_o \text{ dB} \quad (3)$$

AMC (Adaptive Modulation and Coding) process based on modulation from MCS (Modulation and Code Scheme). This research used that MCS consist of QPSK, 16 QAM, dan 64 QAM [15].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research described about communication system of UE that moved around building environment. That buildings used high variation consist of 10m, 15m, and 20m. Building environment caused diffraction mechanism. That diffraction mechanism modeled with single knife edge method. UE moved toward HetNet NBs that consist of Node Base macrocell (NB1) and Node Base microcell (NB2). The communication propagation channel effected by AWGN. AMC was used MCS that consist of QPSK, 16 QAM, and 64 QAM. Code rate of QPSK modulation was used consist of 1/8, 1/5, 1/4, 1/3, 1/2, 2/3, 3/4, and 4/5. Code rate of 16 QAM modulation was used consist of 1/2, 2/3, 3/4, and 4/5. Code rate of 64 QAM modulation was used consist of 2/3, 3/4, and 4/5.

Figure 4 shows about SNR value of NB1 and NB2 with uplink condition. Some data such as UE moved 70m that obtained NB1 13.69 dB and NB2 18.02 dB, awgn NB1 13.69 dB and awgn NB2 15.15 dB. UE moved 230m that obtained NB1 31.98 dB and NB2 -5.85 dB, awgn NB1 47.51 dB and NB2 -5.13 dB. UE moved 550m that obtained NB1 24.44 dB and NB2 29.36 dB, awgn NB1 26.88 dB and NB2 20.45 dB.

Figure. 4 SNR value at NB1 and NB2

Figure. 5 AMC from channel with AWGN

Figure 5 shows about kind of modulation with number initial. Number 15 until number 0 consist of 64 QAM coderate 4/5, 64 QAM coderate 3/4, 64 QAM coderate 2/3, 16 QAM coderate 4/5, 16 QAM coderate 3/4, 16 QAM coderate 2/3, 16 QAM coderate 1/2, QPSK coderate 4/5, QPSK coderate 3/4, QPSK coderate 2/3, QPSK coderate 1/2, QPSK coderate 1/3, QPSK coderate 1/4, QPSK coderate 1/5, QPSK coderate 1/8, and loss (0). Initial 0 (zero) caused SNR value under SNR of QPSK code rate 1/8. That figure showed AMC at NB1, AMC at NB2, and AMC when used selection combining (SC) method. That selection combining used diversity form NBs macrocell and NBs microcell. Some data showed at UE moved 70m that obtained AMC at NB1 used 16 QAM code rate 1/2 or AMC number 9, AMC at NB2 used 16 QAM code rate 4/5 or AMC number 12. UE moved 230m that obtained AMC at NB1 used 64 QAM code rate 4/5 or AMC number 15, AMC at NB2 loss condition, and AMC with SC used 64 QAM code rate 4/5 or AMC number 15. UE moved 550m that obtained AMC at NB1 used 16 QAM code rate 4/5 or AMC number 12, AMC at NB2 used 64 QAM code rate 4/5 or AMC number 15, and AMC with SC used 64 QAM code rate 4/5 or AMC number 15.

Figure. 6 Amount nodes with AMC

Figure. 7 Percentages for used AMC

Number of nodes with AMC can be seen in Figure 6. Number of nodes for QPSK, 16 QAM, and 64 QAM. Amount of QPSK at NB1 obtained 11 nodes, NB2 obtained 22 nodes, and SC obtained 6 nodes. Amount of 16 QAM at NB1 obtained 20 nodes, NB2 obtained 7 nodes, and SC obtained 11 nodes. Amount 64 QAM at NB1 obtained 36 nodes, NB2 obtained 29 nodes, and SC obtained 50 nodes. Amount of 64 QAM code rate 4/5 at NB1 obtained 30 nodes, NB2 obtained 25 nodes, and SC obtained 45 nodes.

The percentages at AMC consist of NB1, NB2, and SC, can be seen in Figure 7. Some data obtained percentages consist of QPSK, 16 QAM, and 64 QAM. Percentages of QPSK obtained NB1 16.42%, NB2 32.86%, and SC 8.96%. Percentages of 16 QAM obtained NB1 29.85%, NB2 10.45%, and SC 16.42%. Percentages of 64 QAM obtained NB1 53.74%, NB2 43.29%, and SC 74.63%. More detail percentages of 64 QAM code rate 4/5 obtained NB1 44.78%, NB2 37.32%, and SC 67.16%. The percentages of coverage area obtained NB1 100%, NB2 86.56%, and SC 100%.

The trajectory UE around building through HetNet cell obtained modulation at AMC that was used. The modulation was used for selection combining consist of UE at 70m obtained 16 QAM code rate 4/5, UE at 230m obtained 16 QAM code rate 4/5, UE at 550m obtained 64 QAM code rate 4/5. The amount nodes covered around trajectory UE with selection combining at 64 QAM of 50 nodes, and 64 QAM code rate 4/5 of 45 nodes. The percentages AMC with SC was used around UE trajectory such as QPSK 8.9%, 16 QAM 16.42%, and 64 QAM 74.62%. The percentages AMC with SC for 64 QAM code rate 4/5 obtained 67.16%. The coverage of trajectory UE obtained 100% for Node Base macrocell, 86.57% for Node Base microcell, and 100% for selection combining.

IV. CONCLUSION

The conclusion for this research about UE communication systems moved around building with 10 GHz through HetNet cell. That building caused diffraction mechanism. Diffraction mechanism modeled with Single Knife Edge method. Propagation channel used AWGN condition. HetNet was used consist of NBs macrocell and NBs microcell. SNR value influenced AMC that was used. AMC mechanism based on MCS that consist of QPSK, 16 QAM, and 64 QAM. As the result was analyze research with some comparison such as Node Base macrocell, Node Base microcell, and selection combining (SC). The coverage percentage when used SC obtained 100%, Node Base macrocell 100%, and Node Base microcell 86.56%. The modulation percentages of SC method with 64 QAM obtained 74.62%, and 64 QAM code rate 4/5 obtained 67.16%.

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